

COMPARATIVE ECONOMICS OF FARMING SYSTEM IN JALNA DISTRICT

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Abstract

In the study on attempt has been made to study the "Comparative Economics of Farming Systems in Jalna District". For this study the, Primary data collected from 60 farmers consisting 30 farmers of each of each farming system (i.e. Crop only farming system and Crop + Livestock farming system). The per hectare use of resources was highest in Crop + Livestock farming system as compared to Crop only farming system. The per hectare used of human labour was highest i.e. 157.12 man-days in Crop + Livestock farming system as compared to Crops only farming system i.e 56.50 man-days. Per hectare used of seed was highest i.e. 49.31 kg in Crop + Livestock farming system as compared to Crops only farming system i.e. 48.11 kg. The per hectare total cost of cultivation was highest in Crop + Livestock farming system i.e. Cost C_3 was Rs. 318580.76 and gross income was Rs. 475720.26 as compared to Crops only farming system i.e. Cost C_3 was Rs. 90848.58 and gross income was 119704.87. The per hectare net profit was maximum in Crop + Livestock farming system (i.e. Rs. 157139.50) as compared to Crops only farming system (i.e. Rs. 28856.29). The study revealed between two farming systems Crop + Livestock farming system was found to be highly profitable farming system than Crops only farming system.

Keywords- Crop, Crop + Livestock, Farming system, Resource, Gross income, Profit

Introduction

Farming system is an integrated set of activities that farmers perform in their farms under their resources and circumstances to maximize the productivity and net farm income on a sustainable basis. The farming system represents an appropriate combination of different farm enterprises viz., cropping systems, livestock, horticulture, forestry, poultry, piggery, fisheries and goat rearing etc., and were the means available to the farmer to raise their profitability. All components of farming systems are interrelated to each other. Alternatively a farming system is defined as a way in which farm resources are allocated subject to the needs and priorities of the farmer in his local circumstances, which include agro-climatic conditions and economic circumstances.

Crop production is subject to a high degree of risk and uncertainty and provides only seasonal, irregular and uncertain income and employment to the farmers. In order to minimize the risk and uncertainties, the farmers are practicing integrated farming system. Farming systems refers to the organization of enterprises on the farm to achieve the maximum income.

Animals can perform numerous functions in small holder systems. They provide products such as meat, milk, eggs, wool etc. They serve socio-cultural functions, as bride wealth, for ceremonial feasts and as gifts or loans, which strengthen social bonds. Integration of livestock into the farming system is particularly important for a) Increasing subsistence security by diversifying the food generating activities of the farm family b) Transferring nutrient and energy between animals and crops via manure and forage from cropped areas via use of draught animals.

Dairy farming is one of the economically viable enterprises that could provide constant income throughout the year to farmers when combined with cropping. The success of dairying depends solely on the availability of inputs like feed and fodder and better marketing facilities to milk. To maximize benefits from dairying selection of proper breed to suit the local conditions is very essential.

Materials and Methods

The present study on Comparative Economics of Farming Systems in Jalna District. Two tehsils viz. Jafrabad and Bhokardan was selected on the basis of availability of potential farming system. In all, six villages i.e. Three villages each from Jafrabad and Bhokardan tehsils, were selected randomly. 10 farmers from each village consisting of 5 Crop and 5 Crop + Livestock farming system were selected. Thus, 60 farmers from 6 villages comprising of 30 Crop only farming system and 30 Crop + Livestock farming systems were selected for study. For the present study, the primary data was collected by survey method from the selected farmers with the help of specially designed schedule

for the year 2021-2022. The data was collected on different aspects such as the family size, land utilization, cropping pattern, capital assets, livestock position, cost and returns from Crop and Crop + Livestock farming system.

Economics of farming systems

Cost and returns of farming system were calculated as per the standardized cost concept.

Cost A_1

It is the actual paid out cost incurred by the farmers. This cost comprise of the expenditure incurred by the farmers in cash as well as kind for the cultivation of crops in respect of following items.

1. Hired human labour (Days)
2. Bullock labour (Days)
3. Machinery charges (Hr)
4. Seed or Planting material (Kg)
5. Manure (Tonnes)
6. Fertilizers (Kg)
7. Plant Protection (Lit)
8. Irrigation charges (Rs)
9. Land revenue and other taxes
10. Interest on working capital
11. Depreciation on implements and farm building

Cost A_2

Cost A_1 + Rent paid for leased inland.

Cost B_1

Cost A_1 + interest value of owned fixed capital assets (excluding land)

Cost B_2

Cost B_1 + Rental value of land

Cost C_1

Cost B_1 + imputed value of family labour

Cost C_2

Cost B_2 + Imputed value of family labour

Cost C_3

Cost C_2 + 10 % of Cost C_2

Gross and Net Income**Gross Income**

Gross income= Value of main produce + Value of by produce

Net income

It is difference between the gross income and the cost of cultivation at different cost concepts.

Input-output Ratio

It is the ratio of gross income and total expenditure incurred.

Results and Discussion**Resource use pattern**

The resource use pattern of any production activity indicates composition of the expenditures incurred on various inputs. It is

useful to locate the strength and weaknesses in the production system so as to increase the efficiency.

Table.1 Per hectare resource use pattern

Sr. No	Particulars	Unit	Farming systems			
			Crop		C+ L	
			qtl	Rs/ha	Qtl	Rs/ha
1	Hired labour	Days	24.74	5663.83	26.14	5946.11
2	Family labour	Days	31.76	7973.58	130.98	36215.00
3	Total labour	Days	56.50	13637.41	157.12	42161.11
4	Bullock labour	Days	5.76	4034.49	6.74	4718.00
5	Machinery	Hrs	9.89	7909.56	10.74	8595.00
6	Seed	Kg	48.11	4858.95	49.31	4908.42
7	Manure	Tonnes	1.80	1799.01	2.65	2650.00
8	Fertilizers					
	N	Kg	140.36	842.14	144.33	865.98
	P	Kg	382.43	4206.71	385.07	4235.77
	K	Kg	76.68	1495.25	80.15	1522.80
	Micronutrients	Kg	3.63	3625.26	4.68	4680.00
	Total		603.09	10169.36	614.23	11304.55
9	Plant protection	Litre	4.82	8377.62	4.91	8396.85
10	Livestock fodder	Kg	-	-	12634.28	100536.11

The average per hectare resources utilization is given in table.1 It is seen from table.1 that the per hectare used of human labour was highest i.e. 157.12 man-days in Crop + Livestock farming system as compared to Crops only farming system i.e. 56.50 man-days.

Per hectare used of machinery was highest i.e. 10.74 hours in Crop + Livestock farming system followed Crops only farming system i.e. 9.89 hours. Per hectare used of seed was highest i.e. 49.31 kg in Crop + Livestock farming system followed by Crops only farming system

i.e. 48.11 kg. Per hectare used of manure was highest i.e. 2.65 tonnes in Crop + Livestock farming system followed by Crops only farming system i.e. 1.80 tonnes. Per hectare use of fertilizers was highest i.e. 614.23 kg in Crop + Livestock farming system as compared to Crop only farming system i.e. 603.09 kg.

The resources use i.e. labour, seeds, fertilizers, machinery, etc. in proposed farming system are in varied proportion.

Expenditure pattern of different farming systems

Table.2 Expenditure pattern of different farming systems (Rs/ha)

Sr. No	Particulars	Farming systems				
		Crop	% of Cost C ₃	C + L	% of Cost C ₃	
1	Hired human labour Male	2152.77	2.37	2156.98	0.68	
	Female	3511.06	3.86	3789.13	1.19	
2	Bullock labour	4034.49	4.44	4718.00	1.48	
3	Machine charges	7909.56	8.71	8595.00	2.70	
4	Seed	4858.95	5.35	4908.42	1.54	
5	Manures	1799.01	1.98	2650.00	0.83	
6	Fertilizer N	842.14	0.93	865.98	0.27	
		P	4206.71	4.63	4235.77	1.33
		K	1495.25	1.65	1522.80	0.48
	Micronutrients	3625.26	3.99	4680.00	1.47	
7	Irrigation charges	2732.95	3.01	3231.59	1.01	
8	Plant protection	8377.62	9.22	8396.85	2.64	
9	Incidental charges	309.55	0.34	367.22	0.12	
10	Repairing charges	393.68	0.43	408.67	0.13	
11	Livestock maintenance	-	-	100536.11	31.56	
12	Working capital (1 to 11)	46249.04	50.91	151062.52	47.42	
13	Interest on working capital @ 6%	2774.94	3.05	9063.75	2.85	
14	Depreciation	3521.37	3.88	5935.81	1.86	
15	Land Revenue	152.80	0.17	154.79	0.05	
16	COST A₁	52698.16	58.01	166216.87	52.17	
17	Rental value of leased land	-	-	-	-	

18	COST A ₂	52698.16	58.01	166216.87	52.17
19	Interest on fixed Capital @ 10% per annum	1992.53	2.19	7926.09	2.49
20	COST B ₁	54690.69	60.20	174142.96	54.66
21	Rental value of land	19925.35	21.93	79260.91	24.88
22	COST B ₂	74616.04	82.13	253403.87	79.54
23	Family human labour Male	4861.25	5.35	30075.00	9.44
	Female	3112.33	3.43	6140.00	1.93
24	COST C ₁	62664.27	68.98	210357.96	66.03
25	COST C ₂	82589.62	90.91	289618.87	90.91
26	10% OF COST C ₂	8258.96	9.09	28961.89	9.09
27	COST C ₃	90848.58	100.00	318580.76	100.00
28	Main Produce	118016.14	-	142201.46	-
29	By Produce	1688.73	-	1613.14	-
30	Livestock (Dairy) Produce	-	-	331905.66	-
31	Total value of Produce	119704.87	-	475720.26	-

(Figures in the parentheses indicates the percentages to cost C₃)

It is revealed from the table.2 that the, in case of Crop only farming system cost A₁, cost A₂, cost B₁, cost B₂, cost C₁, cost C₂ and cost C₃ was Rs. 52698.16, Rs. 52698.16, Rs. 54690.69, Rs.74616.04, Rs. 62664.27, Rs. 82589.62 and Rs. 90848.58 respectively. The Gross return was Rs. 119704.87. The per centage shared of hired human labour, seed and manure was 6.23%, 5.35% and 1.98% respectively. In case of Crop + Livestock farming system, cost A₁, cost A₂, cost B₁, cost B₂, cost C₁, cost C₂ and cost C₃ was Rs. 166216.87, Rs. 166216.87, Rs. 174142.96, Rs. 253403.87, Rs. 210357.96, Rs.

289618.87 and Rs. 318580.76. The Gross return was Rs. 475720.26. The per centage of livestock maintenance was 31.56% in Crop + Livestock farming system. The percentage shared of hired human labour, seed and manure was 1.87%, 1.54% and 0.83% in Crop + Livestock farming system.

Profitability of different farming systems

Profitability of farming systems is important to examine the best farming system in the study area. The information on profitability of different farming system is presented in table.3.

Table.3 Profitability of different farming systems

(Rs/ha)

Sr. No	Particulars	Farming systems	
		Crop	C + L
1	Income (Rs)	119704.87	475720.26
2	Expenditure (Rs)	90848.58	318580.76
3	Profit (Rs)	28856.29	157139.50
4	B:C Ratio	1.32	1.49

It can be seen from the table.3 that, In Crop + Livestock farming system i.e. Rs. 157139.50 per hectare profit was high as compared to Crops only farming system i.e. Rs. 28856.29. The per hectare income of Crop + Livestock farming system i.e. Rs. 475720.26 over Crop only farming system i.e. Rs. 119704.87 over was more. B:C ratio of Crop + Livestock farming system was 1.49 followed by Crop only farming system was 1.32.

To sum up, it can be noted that as farmers shifts from Crop only farming system to Crop + Livestock farming system the income, expenditure and profit goes on increases. It indicates that the Crop + Livestock farming system was economically most viable in Jalna district as compared to Crop only farming systems.

Conclusions

It is concluded from the study that, the per hectare used of human labour was highest in Crop + Livestock farming system (157.12 man-days) followed by Crop only farming system (56.50 man-days). Employment pattern indicates share of wages days in gross farm employment increase as farmer shifts from Crop only farming system to Crop + Livestock farming system. The per hectare total cost of cultivation was highest in Crop + Livestock farming system i.e. Cost C₃ was Rs. 318580.76 and gross income was Rs. 475720.26 as compared to Crops only farming system i.e. Cost C₃ was Rs. 90848.58 and gross income was Rs. 119704.87. In Crop + Livestock farming system per hectare profit (Rs. 157139.50) was high as

compared to Crops only (Rs. 28856.29). B:C ratio of Crop + Livestock farming system was 1.49 followed Crop only farming system was 1.32. Crop + Livestock farming system over Crops only farming system was more profitable. The profitability of farmers, indicates that the Crop + Livestock farming system was economically most viable in Jalna district as compared to Crop only farming system.

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